

out the crop season, but peaks in August. The most severe infestations were recorded in light, sandy soil.

Sporadic Occurrence of two other species, *Popillia cupricollis* Hope (Rutelinae: Scarabaeidae: Coleoptera) and *Holotrichia longipennis* Blanch (Melolonthinae: Scarabaeidae: Coleoptera),

has also been reported. *P. cupricollis* grubs cause damage and beetles chew the rice grains at dough stage.

The 1981 outbreak may have been caused by abnormal rainfall during June, when the beetles emerge, and August, when grubs start damaging the crop. A heavy shower in the third week of June

after a dry spell seems to have triggered simultaneous emergence of adults, which normally emerge over a long period from June through July. Low rainfall during the next 2 weeks encouraged egg-laying and hatching. Intermittent, low rainfall from last week of July through August favored grubs development. □

Occurrence of brown planthopper on *Leersia hexandra* in the Philippines

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In 1982, a brown planthopper (BPH) population which feeds on the weed *Leersia hexandra* was reported in irrigation canals on the IRRI farm. Studies indicated that this population did not feed on rice. A survey was conducted to determine whether the *L. hexandra* population occurred in other areas in the Philippines. *L. hexandra* populations were found in 5 of 11 provinces surveyed (see table) from north to south (see figure).

Occurrence of BPH in *Leersia hexandra* in Philippine provinces.^a

Province	Present (+) or undetected (-)
Pangasinan	+
Cagayan	-
Pampanga	-
Tarlac	-
Nueva Ecija	+
Bulacan	-
Laguna	+
Batangas	-
Quezon	-
Camarines Sur	+
South Cotabato	+

^aFive locations in each province were surveyed.

Locations where *Leersia hexandra* BPH populations were found.

***Leptochloa panicoides* Wight, an occasional host of the yellow rice borer *Scirpophaga incertulas* Walker**

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Yellow rice borer *Scirpophaga incertulas*, a major rice pest, is monophagous with exclusive host specificity to rice. A set of 52 plant species (25 grasses, 12 sedges,

and 15 dicots), which characterize the rice ecosystems of Orissa, were tested with rice (Jaya) for yellow rice borer host potential.

Twenty-five newly hatched first-instar larvae were reared on five stem pieces of each test plant. Stem pieces were replaced every 3 days, surviving larvae were transferred, and larval mortality was recorded. All larvae died within 2 days on 19 grasses, 12 sedges, and 15 dicots, and on 5 more grasses by day 5. The larvae on

Leptochloa panicoides (Gramineae) continued to survive and grow beyond day 15, but died by day 27. Larvae reared on Jaya pupated on day 29.

L. panicoides plants and rice plants grown in earthen pots were infested with 10 neonate larvae/plant. Larvae caused typical deadheart and whitehead symptoms in 8 and 9 days on *L. panicoides* and in 7 days on Jaya. Third- and fourth-instar borer larvae formed typical leaf cases and migrated from *L. panicoides*